

Influence of Stirring on the Velocity and Temperature Coefficient of Photochemical Reactions.

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Attempts have been made from time to time to find out whether the velocity of a homogeneous photochemical reaction is affected by shaking or stirring the reacting substances. So far however, no conclusion has been arrived at from theoretical considerations. In this communication we shall consider this problem from the laws of absorption of light.

Let us consider an absorbing media of thickness l , and I_x be the intensity of light after its passage through the length x of the medium. The amount of the light absorbed

$$= I_0 - I = I_0 (1 - e^{-k'l}) \quad (1)$$

Hence the light absorbed per unit length $= \frac{I_0(1 - e^{-k'l})}{l}$.

If the velocity of the reaction is proportional to the n^{th} power of the light absorption, the average velocity

$$= y_1 = k \left\{ \frac{I_0(1 - e^{-k'l})}{l} \right\}^n \quad (2)$$

This is the average velocity for a reaction, in which the reacting substances are well stirred. If there is no stirring, the velocity of the reaction will vary from place to place with the thickness of the medium according to the variation in light absorption with the thickness of the mixture as given by Lambert's law of absorption. The reaction takes place not only at the places of maximum absorption, but also at places of low absorption, so that the observed velocity is the mean of these velocities at various points along the thickness of the solution. The amount of light absorption by an unit surface

of the solution situated between l and $l + dl$ along the length of the solution is given by

$$I_l - I_{l+dl} = I_0 \{e^{-kl} - e^{-k(l+dl)}\} \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

We can expand this by applying Taylor's theorem

$$f(x+dx) = f(x) + f'(x)dx + \frac{f''(x)d^2x}{2} \dots \dots \dots$$

$$\text{Hence } I_l - I_{l+dl} = -I_0 f'(e^{-kl})dl = I_0 k e^{-kl} dl \quad \dots \quad (b)$$

The absorption per unit length between l and $l+dl$

$$= \frac{I_0 k e^{-kl} dl}{dl} = k e^{-kl} I_0$$

Hence the velocity of the reaction at this place is equal to

$$k_1 (I_0 k e^{-kl})^n$$

If V_2 be the mean average velocity and v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots , be the velocities at different points along the length of the solution of thickness l , then

$$\begin{aligned} V_2 \times l &= v_1 dl + v_2 dl + v_3 dl + \dots \dots \dots \\ &= \int_{l=0}^{l=l} k_1 \cdot (I_0 \cdot k \cdot e^{-kl})^n dl = \int_{l=0}^{l=l} k_1 I_0^n k^n e^{-knl} dl \\ &= k_1 I_0^n k^n \left[\frac{e^{-knl}}{-kn} \right]_{l=0}^{l=l} = k_1 I_0^n k^n \left[\frac{1}{kn} - \frac{e^{-knl}}{kn} \right] \\ &= \frac{k_1}{k^n} I_0^n k^n \left[1 - e^{-knl} \right] = \frac{k_1 I_0^n k^{n-1}}{n} \left[1 - e^{-knl} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the average velocity without stirring is equal to

$$V_2 = \frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n k^{n-1} \left[1 - e^{-knl} \right] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

If the reaction velocity is directly proportional to the light absorption, then $n=1$ and hence

$$V_1 = V_2 = \frac{k_1}{l} I_0 (1 - e^{-kl})$$

or the stirring produces no effect on the velocity of the reaction, and hence on the temperature coefficient. If n is less than unity, then $V_1 \neq V_2$ or

$$k_1 \left\{ \frac{I_0(1-e^{-kl})}{l} \right\}^n \neq \frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n (1-e^{-kl})^n k^{n-1}.$$

From considerations based on the principles of inequalities, it can be proved that when n is less than 1 then

$$k_1 \left\{ \frac{I_0(1-e^{-kl})}{l} \right\}^n > \frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n k^{n-1} (1-e^{-kl})^n$$

for all values of k and l . This shows that the velocity of the reaction for a continuously stirred reaction is greater than the velocity when the substances are not stirred.

In several papers published from our laboratories, it has been shown that the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction depends on its acceleration caused by light. The greater the acceleration, the smaller is the temperature coefficient. Hence the temperature coefficient for the reaction with good stirring which has got higher photochemical acceleration must be less than that for the same reaction when not stirred. This is what has been actually observed. Two interesting cases of variation in the velocities may be considered: (1) when the absorption is low and (2) when the absorption is very high. When the absorption is very high, $kl = \infty$ and $e^{-kl} = 0$. When the absorption is very low e^{-kl} can be expanded. Thus for continuous stirring we get from (a)

$$V_1 = k_1 \left(\frac{I_0}{l} \right)^n$$

and for the unstirred reaction we have

$$V_2 = \frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n k^{n-1}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{V_1}{V_2} &= \frac{k_1 \left(\frac{I_0}{l} \right)^n}{\frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n k^{n-1}} = \frac{k_1 I_0^n l^n n}{k_1 I_0^n l^n k^{n-1}} = \frac{n}{l^{n-1} k^{n-1}} \\ &= n \cdot (kl)^{1-n} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (A) \end{aligned}$$

but $kl = \infty$. Or the ratio of these two velocities of stirred and unstirred reaction is very high and hence there must be marked variation in temperature coefficients in the two cases.

When the absorption is very low

$$e^{-kl} = 1 - kl + \frac{(kl)^2}{1.2} - \frac{(kl)^3}{1.2.3} \dots$$

Then for the stirred reaction

$$V_1 = k_1 \left\{ \frac{I_0(1 - 1 + kl)}{l} \right\} = k_1 \cdot k^n I_0^n$$

and for unstirred reaction,

$$\begin{aligned} V_2 &= \frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n k^{n-1} \left\{ 1 - 1 + knl \right\} \\ &= \frac{k_1}{nl} I_0^n k^{n-1} knl = k_1 I_0^n k^n. \end{aligned}$$

Hence
$$\frac{V_1}{V_2} = \frac{k_1 k^n I_0^n}{k_1 k^n I_0^n} = 1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(B)}$$

or the velocity of the unstirred reaction is the same as the velocity of the same reaction when stirred. Thus the ratio of the two velocities can vary from infinity to unity depending on the amount of absorption. This clearly shows that what a great amount of variation in temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction is possible under the two circumstances, when the velocity of the reaction is not directly proportional to the light absorption. The equation shows that the velocity of a reaction under both the circumstances depends on the thickness of the solution. The greater the length of the solution, the smaller is the average absorption and hence the velocity is small.

Moreover the shape of the vessel in which the solutions are exposed to light also exert a marked effect on the absorption and on the velocity of the reaction. This leads to a variation in the temperature coefficient with change in the size and shape of the reaction vessel. Hence whenever the results of two workers on the

same reaction are to be compared and when the reaction is not directly proportional to the light absorption, attention should be paid to their experimental conditions as regards the thickness and the shape of the reaction vessel.

The observations of Bhattacharya and Dhar that the relation between intensity and velocity for a particular reaction is not a constant factor but depends upon the amount of photochemical acceleration is highly interesting from the above viewpoint. As the absorption decreases, the photochemical acceleration falls, and the relation between intensity and velocity approaches direct relationship or the effect of stirring goes on decreasing till with very small absorption, the stirring has got practically no effect. This is what is actually expressed by $v_1/v_2=1$ for small absorptions, when n approaches unity.

Regarding the experimental confirmation of the foregoing deductions the only experiments performed are those by Young and Style (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, **27**, 494) on the influence of stirring on the photochemical reaction between iodine and potassium oxalate. They have observed a marked decrease of the temperature coefficient when the mixture is well stirred.

We have also studied the influence of stirring on the velocity of the same photochemical reaction and we have observed that the velocity of the reaction is increased on stirring.

Berthoud and Bellenot (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, **7**, 307), Briers, Chapman and Walters (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 526) and Mukerji and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 1308) observed that the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine and ammonium oxalate and iodine is nearly proportional to the square root of the incident radiation. Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 473) have shown for the same reaction that when the photochemical acceleration is not large and an aqueous solution of iodine is used and KI is not added and the mixture is illuminated by radiations of wave-lengths 5650Å, and 7304Å, the reaction tends to be directly proportional to the light intensity. We are investigating the influence of stirring under the conditions when the reactions tend to be directly proportional to light intensity and we expect to get only very slight variation of the velocity of the reaction with stirring. We are also investigating the influence of stirring on other photochemical reactions.

Summary.

We have deduced from the laws of light absorption a relation which states that when the relation between the light absorption and velocity of the reaction deviates markedly from unity, stirring will lead to increased velocity and decreased temperature coefficient. When the relation between intensity and velocity of the reaction is unity, stirring should have no effect on the velocity and temperature coefficient.

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